

Campus Research Computing Consortium

2025 Research Computing and Data Workforce Survey Questions and Response Items

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This document contains the survey questions used by the Campus Research Computing Consortium's (CaRCC's) [Professionalization Working Group](#) and The Pennsylvania State University for an IRB approved human subjects research survey of individuals within the Research Computing and Data (RCD) workforce in the United States and Canada.

This survey contributes to the existing literature by providing a focused analysis of the RCD workforce with the following objectives:

- Provide an updated understanding of the RCD workforce
- Analyze the complexities of RCD positions
- Investigate RCD Facilitation challenges that take the most effort to manage

Eligible participants included individuals over the age of 18 within the United States or Canada that identified as working in Research Computing and Data (RCD) roles.

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2025 RCD Workforce Survey

Survey Flow

Standard: About The Survey (1 Question)
Standard: Demographics (14 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If

If How old are you? You must be over the age of 18 to complete this survey Under 18 Is Selected

EndSurvey: Advanced

Branch: New Branch

If

If Do you currently reside in the United States or Canada? Why we are asking: At this time this surv... No Is Selected

EndSurvey: Advanced

Standard: Career and Educational Background (17 Questions)
Standard: Current Role (19 Questions)
Standard: RCDResFac (7 Questions)
Standard: Complexity of RCD Roles (7 Questions)
Standard: RCD Facilitation (5 Questions)
Standard: End of Survey Text (1 Question)

Page Break

Start of Block: About The Survey

T_About **About this Survey** The Research Computing and Data (RCD) field continues to evolve rapidly, as does the need to better understand the people who power it. That's why the CaRCC RCD Professionalization Working Group is launching the 2025 RCD Workforce Survey—an effort to gather insights into the roles, characteristics, and job activities of professionals supporting research computing and data across institutions in the United States and Canada. Your honest responses to this survey will help to advance and inform the RCD profession. This research is approved by the Penn State IRB STUDY00027126.

Completing the survey will enter you into a drawing to win one of 20 gift cards (\$75 or \$100 value) - you must complete the survey to be considered. You will be prompted to provide your name and email on a separate Google Form at the end of the survey. This data will be stored separately from survey data. Survey responses are anonymous and will be kept confidential.

End of Block: About The Survey

Start of Block: Demographics

T_Dem **The following set of questions ask about your personal characteristics.** These questions help us build a clearer picture of the research computing and data (RCD) workforce. We know this information may feel potentially identifying. **Data will never be reported individually. Data is only reported in aggregate, never in a way that could identify you.** If fewer than 10 individuals share a particular combination of responses, we will not report that data individually. Instead, it will be grouped or excluded to protect your privacy.

Page Break

Age How old are you? *You must be over the age of 18 to complete this survey*

- Under 18 (4)
- 18 - 24 (5)
- 25-34 (6)
- 35-44 (7)
- 45 - 54 (8)
- 55 - 64 (9)
- 65 or older (10)

Skip To: End of Block If Age = Under 18

Res1 Do you currently reside in the United States or Canada? *Why we are asking: At this time this survey is limited to individuals residing in Canada or the United States.*

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Skip To: End of Block If Res1 = No

Display this question:

If Res1 = Yes

Res2 Where do you reside?

- United States (1)
 - Canada (2)
-

US_Citizen Are you a citizen of the United States or Canada? *Why we are asking: We can better advocate for resources for those that may need visa support.*

- U.S. Citizen (1)
- Canadian Citizen (4)
- Dual U.S. and Canadian Citizen (6)
- Citizen of another country (5)
- Decline to answer (3)

Page Break

Gender Do you describe yourself as a man, a woman, or in some other way? *Why we are asking: This information helps us customize our recruitment and development efforts.*

- Man (1)
 - Woman (2)
 - Some other way (3)
 - Decline to answer (4)
-

Display this question:

If Gender = Some other way

Gender_Other How do you describe yourself?

- Trans man/Transgender male / Female-to-Male (FTM) (1)
 - Trans Woman/Transgender female / Male-to-Female (MTF) (2)
 - Nonbinary / Gender-fluid /Genderqueer / Neither exclusively male nor female (3)
 - Something not listed (please specify) (4)
-
- Don't know / Not Sure (5)
-

RaceEth Which is your race and/or ethnicity? Please select all that apply. *Why we are asking: This information helps up customize our recruitment and development efforts.*

- Hispanic or Latino.** For example, Mexican, Puerto Rican, Salvadoran, Cuban, Dominican, Guatemalan, etc. (1)
 - White.** For example, English, German, Irish, Italian, Polish, Scottish, etc. (2)
 - Black or African American.** For example, African American, Jamaican, Haitian, Nigerian, Ethiopian, Somali, Etc. (3)
 - Asian.** For example, Chinese, Asian Indian, Filipino, Vietnamese, Korean, Japanese, etc. (4)
 - Middle Eastern or North African.** For example, Lebanese, Iranian, Egyptian, Syrian, Iraqi, Israeli, etc. (5)
 - American Indian or Alaska Native.** For example, Navajo Nation, Native Village of Inupiat, Traditional Government, Nome Eskimo Community, Aztec, Maya, etc. (6)
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander.** For example, Native Hawaiian, Samoan, Chamorro, Tongan, Fijian, Marhallese, etc. (7)
 - Don't know / not sure (8)
 - Decline to answer (9)
-

SexualOrientation Do you think of yourself as...? *Why we are asking: This information helps us customize our recruitment and development efforts.*

- Straight or heterosexual (1)
- Lesbian, gay, or homosexual (2)
- Bisexual (3)
- Something else not listed (4)
- Don't know / not sure (5)
- Decline to answer (6)

Page Break

Display this question:

If SexualOrientation = Something else not listed

SexualOrientation_O Which of the following best describes you? Select all that apply.

- Asexual / Graysexual (1)
 - Aromantic (2)
 - Biromantic / Demiromantic / Panromantic (3)
 - Demisexual (4)
 - Fluid (5)
 - Pansexual (6)
 - Polysexual (7)
 - Queer (8)
 - Questioning / Curious (9)
 - Something else not listed (please specify) (10)
-
- Don't know / not sure (11)
 - Decline to answer (12)
-

Vet Are you a military veteran? *Why we are asking: This information helps us customize our recruitment and development efforts.*

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Decline to answer (3)
-

Neurodiverse Do you identify as neurodiverse? *Neurodiverse is a term that refers to individuals whose brains process information differently, including conditions such as autism, ADHD, dyslexia, and other cognitive differences, recognizing that these variations are a part of normal human diversity. This may include people who are formally diagnosed, self-identified, or exploring whether they may be neurodiverse.*

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Decline to answer (3)
-

Disability_Bin Do you identify as a person with a disability or other chronic condition? *A chronic condition is a long-lasting condition that substantially limits one or more of your major life activities.*

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
 - Decline to answer (3)
-

Display this question:

If Disability_Bin = Yes

Disability_Specific How would you describe your disability or chronic condition? Select all that apply

- Blind or visually impaired (1)
 - Deaf or hard of hearing (2)
 - Health-related disability (3)
 - Learning disability (4)
 - Mental health condition (5)
 - Mobility-related disability (6)
 - Speech-related disability (7)
 - Other (please specify) (8)
-

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Career and Educational Background

T_CareerEd **The following set of questions will ask you about your employment and educational background.** We want to better understand the educational pathways and professional experiences that lead individuals to roles in research computing and data (RCD).

Page Break

Degree What is the highest degree you have earned?

- High school or less than high school (1)
- Some College (2)
- 2-year degree (3)
- 4-year degree (4)
- Master's degree (5)
- PhD or Doctorate (6)
- Other (7) _____

Page Break

CIP2Digit In which field(s) or discipline(s) have you earned a degree? Select all that apply. Do not include minors or certifications.

- Agricultural/animal/plant/veterinary science and related fields (01)
- Architecture and related services (04)
- Area, ethnic, cultural, gender, and group studies (05)
- Basic skills and developmental/remedial education (32)
- Biological and biomedical sciences (26)
- Business, management, marketing, and related support services (52)
- Citizenship activities (33)
- Communication, journalism, and related programs (09)
- Communications technologies/technicians and support services (10)
- Computer science and information sciences and support services (11)
- Construction trades (46)
- Culinary, entertainment, and personal services (12)
- Education (13)
- Engineering (14)
- Engineering/engineering-related technologies/technicians (15)
- English language and literature/letters (23)
- Family and consumer sciences/human sciences (19)

- Foreign languages, literatures, and linguistics (16)
- Health professions and related programs (51)
- Health professions residency/fellowship programs (60)
- Health-related knowledge and skills (34)
- History (54)
- Homeland security, law enforcement, firefighting and related protective services (43)
- Interpersonal and social skills (35)
- Legal professions and studies (22)
- Leisure and recreational activities (36)
- Liberal arts and sciences, general studies and humanities (24)
- Library science (25)
- Mathematics and statistics (27)
- Mechanic and repair technologies/technicians (47)
- Medical residency/fellowship programs (61)
- Military science, leadership and operational art (28)
- Military technologies and applied sciences (29)
- Multi/interdisciplinary studies (30)
- Natural resources and conservation (03)

- Parks, recreation, leisure, fitness, and kinesiology (31)
- Personal awareness and self-improvement (37)
- Philosophy and religious studies (38)
- Physical sciences (40)
- Precision production (48)
- Psychology (42)
- Public administration and social service professions (44)
- Science technologies/technicians (41)
- Social sciences (45)
- Theology and religious vocations (39)
- Transportation and materials moving (49)
- Visual and performing arts (50)
- Other, please specify (99)

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Other, please specify

CIP2Digit_Other Please specify the other field or discipline in which you have earned a degree.

Page Break

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Agricultural/animal/plant/veterinary science and related fields

CIP_01 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn an **Agricultural/animal/plant/veterinary science or related field** degree?

- Agriculture, General (01.00)
- Agricultural and Domestic Animal Services (01.05)
- Agricultural and Food Products Processing (01.04)
- Agricultural Business and Management (01.01)
- Agricultural Mechanization (01.02)
- Agricultural Production Operations (01.03)
- Agricultural Public Services (01.08)
- Agriculture/Veterinary Preparatory Programs (01.13)
- Animal Sciences (01.09)
- Applied Horticulture and Horticultural Business Services (01.06)
- Food Science and Technology (01.10)
- International Agriculture (01.07)
- Plant Sciences (01.11)
- Soil Sciences (01.12)
- Veterinary Administrative Services (01.82)
- Veterinary Biomedical and Clinical Sciences (01.81)
- Veterinary Medicine (01.80)

Veterinary/Animal Health Technologies/Technicians (01.83)

Agricultural/Animal/Plant/Veterinary Science and Related Fields, Other (01.99)

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Biological and biomedical sciences

CIP_26 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn a **Biological and biomedical sciences** degree?

- Biology, General (26.01)
 - Biochemistry, Biophysics and Molecular Biology (26.02)
 - Biomathematics, Bioinformatics, and Computational Biology (26.11)
 - Biotechnology (26.12)
 - Botany/Plant Biology (26.03)
 - Cell/Cellular Biology and Anatomical Sciences (26.04)
 - Ecology, Evolution, Systematics, and Population Biology (26.13)
 - Genetics (26.08)
 - Microbiological Sciences and Immunology (26.05)
 - Molecular Medicine (26.14)
 - Neurobiology and Neurosciences (26.15)
 - Pharmacology and Toxicology (26.10)
 - Physiology, Pathology and Related Sciences (26.09)
 - Zoology/Animal Biology (26.07)
 - Biological and Biomedical Sciences, Other (26.99)
-

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Computer science and information sciences and support services

X→

CIP_11 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn a **Computer and information sciences and support services** degree?

- Computer and Information Sciences, General (11.01)
- Computer Programming (11.02)
- Computer Science (11.07)
- Computer Software and Media Applications (11.08)
- Computer Systems Analysis (11.05)
- Computer Systems Networking and Telecommunications (11.09)
- Computer/Information Technology Administration and Management (11.10)
- Data Entry/Microcomputer Applications (11.06)
- Data Processing (11.03)
- Information Science/Studies (11.04)
- Computer and Information Sciences and Support Services, Computer and information sciences and support services, Other (11.99)

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Engineering

X→

CIP_14 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn an **Engineering** degree?

- Engineering, General (14.01)
- Aerospace, Aeronautical, and Astronautical/Space Engineering (14.02)
- Agricultural Engineering (14.03)
- Architectural Engineering (14.04)
- Biochemical Engineering (14.43)
- Biological/Biosystems Engineering (14.45)
- Biomedical/Medical Engineering (14.05)
- Ceramic Sciences and Engineering (14.06)
- Chemical Engineering (14.07)
- Civil Engineering (14.08)
- Computer Engineering (14.09)
- Construction Engineering (14.33)
- Electrical and Computer Engineering (14.47)
- Electrical, Electronics, and Communications Engineering (14.10)
- Electromechanical Engineering (14.41)
- Energy Systems Engineering (14.48)
- Engineering Chemistry (14.44)
- Engineering Mechanics (14.11)

- Engineering Physics (14.12)
- Engineering Science (14.13)
- Environmental/Environmental Health Engineering (14.14)
- Forest Engineering (14.34)
- Geological/Geophysical Engineering (14.39)
- Industrial Engineering (14.35)
- Manufacturing Engineering (14.36)
- Materials Engineering (14.18)
- Mechanical Engineering (14.19)
- Mechatronics, Robotics, and Automation Engineering (14.42)
- Metallurgical Engineering (14.20)
- Mining and Mineral Engineering (14.21)
- Naval Architecture and Marine Engineering (14.22)
- Nuclear Engineering (14.23)
- Ocean Engineering (14.24)
- Operations Research (14.37)
- Paper Science and Engineering (14.40)
- Petroleum Engineering (14.25)

- Polymer/Plastics Engineering (14.32)
 - Surveying Engineering (14.38)
 - Systems Engineering (14.27)
 - Textile Sciences and Engineering (14.28)
 - Engineering, Other (14.99)
-

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Engineering/engineering-related technologies/technicians

X→

CIP_15 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn an **Engineering/engineering-related technologies/technicians** degree?

- Engineering Technologies/Technicians, General (15.00)
- Architectural Engineering Technologies/Technicians (15.01)
- Civil Engineering Technologies/Technicians (15.02)
- Computer Engineering Technologies/Technicians (15.12)
- Construction Engineering Technology/Technician (15.10)
- Drafting/Design Engineering Technologies/Technicians (15.13)
- Electrical/Electronic Engineering Technologies/Technicians (15.03)
- Electromechanical Technologies/Technicians (15.04)
- Energy Systems Technologies/Technicians (15.17)
- Engineering-Related Fields (15.15)
- Engineering-Related Technologies/Technicians (15.11)
- Environmental Control Technologies/Technicians (15.05)
- Industrial Production Technologies/Technicians (15.06)
- Mechanical Engineering Related Technologies/Technicians (15.08)
- Mining and Petroleum Technologies/Technicians (15.09)
- Nanotechnology (15.16)
- Nuclear Engineering Technology/Technician (15.14)

- Quality Control and Safety Technologies/Technicians (15.07)
- Engineering/Engineering-Related Technologies/Technicians, Other (15.99)

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Physical sciences

CIP_40 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn a **Physical sciences** degree?

- Physical Sciences, General (40.01)
- Astronomy and Astrophysics (40.02)
- Atmospheric Sciences and Meteorology (40.04)
- Chemistry (40.05)
- Geological and Earth Sciences/Geosciences (40.06)
- Materials Sciences (40.10)
- Physics (40.08)
- Physics and Astronomy (40.11)
- Physical Sciences, Other (40.99)

Display this question:

If CIP2Digit = Social sciences

CIP_45 In which specific field(s) or discipline(s) did you earn a **Social sciences** degree?

- Social Sciences, General (45.01)
- Anthropology (45.02)
- Archeology (45.03)
- Criminology (45.04)
- Demography (45.05)
- Economics (45.06)
- Geography and Anthropology (45.15)
- Geography and Cartography (45.07)
- International Relations and National Security Studies (45.09)
- Political Science and Government (45.10)
- Rural Sociology (45.14)
- Sociology (45.11)
- Sociology and Anthropology (45.13)
- Urban Studies/Affairs (45.12)
- Social Sciences, Other (45.99)

Page Break

Display this question:

If In which field(s) or discipline(s) have you earned a degree? Select all that apply. Do not inclu...
q://QID47/SelectedChoicesCount Is Greater Than 1

Carry Forward Selected Choices from "CIP2Digit"

CIP2DigitHighest In which field or discipline did you earn your highest degree?

- Agricultural/animal/plant/veterinary science and related fields (1)
- Architecture and related services (2)
- Area, ethnic, cultural, gender, and group studies (3)
- Basic skills and developmental/remedial education (4)
- Biological and biomedical sciences (5)
- Business, management, marketing, and related support services (6)
- Citizenship activities (7)
- Communication, journalism, and related programs (8)
- Communications technologies/technicians and support services (9)
- Computer science and information sciences and support services (10)
- Construction trades (11)
- Culinary, entertainment, and personal services (12)
- Education (13)
- Engineering (14)
- Engineering/engineering-related technologies/technicians (15)
- English language and literature/letters (16)
- Family and consumer sciences/human sciences (17)
- Foreign languages, literatures, and linguistics (18)
- Health professions and related programs (19)
- Health professions residency/fellowship programs (20)
- Health-related knowledge and skills (21)

- History (22)
- Homeland security, law enforcement, firefighting and related protective services (23)
- Interpersonal and social skills (24)
- Legal professions and studies (25)
- Leisure and recreational activities (26)
- Liberal arts and sciences, general studies and humanities (27)
- Library science (28)
- Mathematics and statistics (29)
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- Military science, leadership and operational art (32)
- Military technologies and applied sciences (33)
- Multi/interdisciplinary studies (34)
- Natural resources and conservation (35)
- Parks, recreation, leisure, fitness, and kinesiology (36)
- Personal awareness and self-improvement (37)
- Philosophy and religious studies (38)
- Physical sciences (39)
- Precision production (40)
- Psychology (41)
- Public administration and social service professions (42)

- Science technologies/technicians (43)
- Social sciences (44)
- Theology and religious vocations (45)
- Transportation and materials moving (46)
- Visual and performing arts (47)
- Other, please specify (48)

Page Break

RelateDgre How **closely related** is one or more of your degree(s) to your current job? *If you are not currently employed, please answer based on your most recent job.*

- Directly related (1)
 - Somewhat related (2)
 - Unrelated (3)
-

ProfCert Do you have any professional certifications or licenses that are related to your work? *For example, Red Hat, Project Management Professional, AWS, Cisco, etc.*

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Page Break

FTYears How many **total years** of **full-time professional experience** do you have? *Do not include positions held as part of a degree program (e.g, graduate assistant roles). DO count post-doc positions. If less than 1 one year, please enter zero.*

Page Break

T_RCDResp **Research Computing and Data (RCD) professional responsibilities** encompass managing or supporting computational resources, data storage or management systems, specialized software, and/or other related resources, services, and technologies that are used to enable scientific research.

FTYearsRCD Based on the definition above, how many **total years of full-time professional experience do you have working as a Research Computing and Data (RCD) professional?** *This number is likely the same as, or a proportion of your response to the last question. If less than one year, please enter zero.*

Page Break

End of Block: Career and Educational Background

Start of Block: Current Role

T_CrntRole **The following set of questions will ask you about your current position.** We want to better understand the professional landscape of the research computing and data (RCD) workforce, including the types of organizations RCD professionals work in, the nature of their roles, and how these roles are structured and funded. We know this information may feel potentially identifying. **Data will never be reported individually. Data is only reported in aggregate, never in a way that could identify you.** If fewer than 10 individuals share a particular combination of responses, we will not report that data individually. Instead, it will be grouped or excluded to protect your privacy.

Page Break

EmpStatus Which of the following best describes your current employment status?

- Employed full-time (1)
 - Employed part-time (2)
 - Self-employed (e.g., independent contractor) (3)
 - Not currently employed (4)
 - On leave (e.g., parental leave, medical leave, sabbatical, etc.) (5)
 - Retired (6)
 - Other (please specify) (7)
-

Skip To: End of Block If EmpStatus = Not currently employed

OrgType Which best describes your current place of work?

- Institution of Higher Education (2)
 - Government agency / research lab (4)
 - Non-profit or non-governmental organization (1)
 - For-profit company (3)
 - K-12 School (5)
 - Self-employed (6)
 - Other (please specify) (7)
-

OrgName What is the name of the organization where you currently work? *Why we are asking: We are using this information for benchmarking positions across organizations. Identifying information will not be reported alongside organizational information.*

Page Break

OrgLoc What is the ZIP or postal code for your organization's primary location? *Location information will be used for comparisons to local labor markets and cost of living adjustments.*

Page Break

PositHrs Which of the following best describes your position status?

- Full-Time (typically 40 hours/week) (1)
 - Three-quarter time (typically 30hrs/week or 0.75 FTE) (4)
 - Half-time (typically 20hr/week) (2)
 - Less than half-time (5)
-

PositWage Is your current position hourly or salaried?

- Hourly - paid based on hours worked (1)
 - Salaried, Exempt - **Not** eligible for overtime pay (2)
 - Salaried, Non-Exempt, eligible for overtime pay (4)
 - Other (please specify) (3)
-

WrkArg Which of the following best describes your current work arrangement?

- Fully On-site (I work on-site all the time) (1)
 - Hybrid (I split my time between remote and on-site work) (2)
 - Fully Remote (I work remotely all the time) (3)
-

Page Break

Careerlvl Which of the below best represents your current career level?

- Intern - Student or trainee (1)
- Entry - New to the field (2)
- Mid-career - Experienced in the field (3)
- Senior - Expert in the field (4)
- Executive (e.g., director, AVP) - Strategic leadership (5)
- Other (please specify) (7)

Page Break

PositScope What is the **primary scope** of your responsibilities in your current position? *We are asking about the level of the organization where you are typically focused/working.*

- Study team/research group or lab (1)
 - Department/Center (2)
 - College/Institute (3)
 - Institution-wide - Across a single institution/organization (4)
 - Regional - Across multiple organizations in a given region (5)
 - National - Across a country (6)
 - International - Across multiple countries (7)
-

WrkDirRes Do you **interact directly** with researchers or research teams? *Including graduate students, post-docs, research staff, and faculty researchers.*

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Display this question:
If OrgType = Institution of Higher Education

WrkUnit What type of unit do you work within? *For example, Central IT, Libraries, Research Institute or Center, Academic college/department, Medical or Health Sciences Unit*

Page Break

JobTitle What is your current **job title** for your primary position? *We are asking about the title that you usually go by, sometimes called "working" or "business" title.*

PrimaryPosit Which of the below categories best describes your current **primary position**? *We are asking about your job profile or classification.*

- Research/Scientific Staff (1)
 - Information Technology Staff (2)
 - Engineering Staff (3)
 - Business Administration Staff (4)
 - Administration/Leadership (5)
 - Non-tenure Faculty (6)
 - Tenure-line Faculty (7)
 - Adjunct Faculty (8)
 - Post doctoral Fellow (9)
 - Student Role (10)
 - Emeritus (11)
 - Something else (Please specify) (12)
-

Page Break

GrossIncome **What is your annual gross income for your current primary position?**
Please enter a number in U.S. Dollars. Do not include a dollar sign. If you need to convert to U.S. Dollars, please visit <https://fiscaldata.treasury.gov/currency-exchange-rates-converter>

Annual gross income in U.S. Dollars (\$) (1)

Page Break

PositFund How is your position funded?

- Institutional/General Funds (i.e., "Hard Funding") (1)
- Sponsored Funds (i.e., "Soft Funding") (2)
- A combination of institutional and sponsored funds (3)
- Not sure/Don't know (4)

Page Break

YrsCurrentOrg How long have you worked at your current organization?

- Less than 1 year (1)
 - 1-2 years (2)
 - 3-5 years (3)
 - 6-10 years (4)
 - 11-15 years (5)
 - 16-20 years (6)
 - More than 20 years (7)
-

PositProm How many times have you been promoted or changed your position at your current institution?

- Never (0)
 - Once (1)
 - Twice (2)
 - Three times (3)
 - Four or more times (4)
-

PositPT In addition to your full-time primary employment, do you have any other additional paid jobs or positions? *Regardless of if the additional job is related to your current work or education.*

Yes (1)

No (2)

End of Block: Current Role

Start of Block: RCDResFac

T_RCD The following set of questions will ask you about the concepts of Research Computing and Data (RCD) responsibilities and the CaRCC Facings. We want to know how RCD professionals describe the work that they do and whether they are familiar with a framework called the CaRCC Facings. Your responses will help us understand how widely the model is known and whether it aligns with your actual responsibilities.

CaRCCFacing Are you familiar with the CaRCC Facings Model?

Yes (1)

No (2)

RCDFam Before taking this survey, were you familiar with the term "Research Computing and Data" or "RCD" professional?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Page Break

T_RCDResp **Research Computing and Data professional responsibilities** encompass managing or supporting computational resources, data storage systems, specialized software, and/or related resources, services, and technologies to help research study teams conduct science.

%RCDResp What percentage of your position is dedicated to Research Computing and Data (RCD) responsibilities? *Please enter a value between 0 - 100. Do not enter a '%' symbol.*

Skip To: End of Survey If Condition: What percentage of your pos... Is Equal to 0. Skip To: End of Survey.

Page Break

Display this question:

If CaRCCFacing = No

T_Facings **The CaRCC Facings Model** describes that RCD roles can be grouped into five (non-mutually exclusive) focus areas called "Facings." In other words, "Facings" describe who or what your role is facing (i.e., focused on). The Five Facings are: **Researcher-Facing: You work directly with researchers and researcher teams.** Examples include: *Research IT User Support, Research Computing Facilitator, Research Data Consultant.* **Systems-Facing: You work directly with systems.** Examples include: *HPC systems engineer, Storage Engineer, Network Engineer.* **Data-Facing: You work directly with data.** Examples include: *Research Management specialist, Data Librarian, Data Scientist, etc.* **Software-Facing: You work directly with software.** Example roles include: *Research Software Engineer, Applications Specialist, Data Engineer, etc.* **Strategy and Policy-Facing: You work directly with strategy and policy.** Example roles include: *Senior Director, Director, Assistant/Associate Director, AVP, CIO, etc.*

Display this question:

If *What percentage of your position is dedicated to Research Computing and Data (RCD) responsibilities? Please enter a value between 0 - 100. Do not enter a % symbol. Text Response Is Not Equal to 0*

%Facing For the part of your job that is focused on **RCD responsibilities, what percentage of your time is focused on each Facing?** *Responses must equal to 100*

Researcher-Facing : _____ (1)

Systems-Facing : _____ (2)

Data-Facing : _____ (3)

Software-Facing : _____ (4)

Strategy and Policy-Facing : _____ (5)

Total : _____

End of Block: RCDResFac

Start of Block: Complexity of RCD Roles

T_RCDRole **This next section will ask you questions about specific activities you perform in your Research Computing and Data (RCD) role.** We want to better understand activities research computing and data (RCD) professionals perform to assess the variety, depth, and complexity of responsibilities in these roles.

RCD20% What are the top five activities that you spend the most of your time on? Enter the numbers 1 through 5 in the boxes provided, where: 1 = The type of activity you spend the most of your time on.

- _____ System operations, management, maintenance and upgrades (1)
- _____ Security management (2)
- _____ Monitoring and troubleshooting (17)
- _____ Code development and review (16)
- _____ Automation and scripting (3)
- _____ Documentation (18)
- _____ Writing reports, articles, proposals, etc. (21)
- _____ Data management, engineering, curation, data science, data visualization, statistical analyses (4)
- _____ Project, program, portfolio management (6)
- _____ User support, consultation, requirements gathering, education, training (8)
- _____ Community building, outreach (10)
- _____ Grant management, submitting reports, financial management and compliance (13)
- _____ Meetings, coordination, facilitation (23)
- _____ Supervision, hiring, performance management (14)
- _____ Planning, developing policy, strategy, organizational goals (15)
- _____ Something else not listed (19)
- _____ Something else not listed (20)

Page Break

GenSpec Would you say you are more of a generalist or a specialist?

- More of a generalist - I often wear multiple hats, and engage in a wide array of skills and activities (1)
 - More of a specialist - I primarily focus on a distinct set of activities or skills (2)
-

DirRes Do you directly contribute to research projects or other scholarly activities?

- Yes (1)
 - No (2)
-

Page Break

RCDTech Which research, computing, or data technologies do you typically support?

- Advanced Computing (e.g., High-performance, High-throughput, etc.) (1)
 - Computer Labs (Virtual or Physical Machines) (2)
 - Coding/Analysis environments (e.g., notebooks) (10)
 - Commercial Cloud (3)
 - Data Visualization tools (4)
 - Research Data Management/Movement Tools (5)
 - Large-scale Data Storage (8)
 - Research Software/Workflow/Automation (6)
 - Other (please specify) (9)
-

Page Break

RCDActFreq How **often** do you engage in the following activities as part of your RCD work?

	Rarely - Less than once a month (2)	Sometimes - At least once a month (3)	Often - Weekly (4)	Very Often - Daily (5)	Not Applicable (11)
Learn new technologies to perform your job (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bridge gaps between researchers and IT (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Encounter complex problems that require extensive troubleshooting or research to resolve (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Switch between multiple projects in a given day (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provide highly customized (bespoke) solutions (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q84 What part of your RCD work do you find most complex? Why? *This could relate to technical tasks, interpersonal dynamics, organizational politics, compliance requirements, or something else.*

End of Block: Complexity of RCD Roles

Start of Block: RCD Facilitation

T_RCDFac **RCD Professional responsibilities** encompass managing or supporting computational resources, data storage systems, specialized software, and/or related resources, services, and technologies to help research study teams conduct science. **RCD Facilitation** (sometimes called CI Facilitation) is a subset of RCD professional responsibilities. **The following questions ask specifically about RCD Facilitation.**

Q67 What percent of your current position is related to RCD Facilitation? Please enter a value between 0 - 100. Do not enter a '%' symbol. *RCD Facilitation involves directly working with researchers to better leverage research computing and data resources for themselves through facilitation, training, and other engagement strategies and tactics.*

Skip To: End of Survey If Condition: What percent of your curren... Is Equal to 0. Skip To: End of Survey.

FacEngage How **often** do you engage with the following stakeholder groups as part of your RCD Facilitation work?

	Rarely - Less than once a month (3)	Sometimes - At least once a month (4)	Often - Weekly (7)	Very Often - Daily (5)	Not Applicable (10)
Principal Investigators (PIs)/Researchers (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Graduate Students (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Postdoctoral Scholars (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research Staff (e.g., techs) (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IT professionals (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
RCD Professionals (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data Managers/Stewards (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Software Engineers/Developers (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Grants/Compliance Professionals (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Engageltns When working directly with researchers or research teams, how **intensive** are your typical interactions?

- Informational** - I provide or receive basic information with minimal discussion (1)
- Supportive** - I assist with tasks or answer questions without deep involvement (2)
- Collaborative** - I work jointly with stakeholders to solve problems or design solutions (3)
- Advisory** - I guide stakeholders, influence decisions, or help shape workflows (4)
- Leading/Coordinating** - I lead or coordinate across multiple groups, managing complex or cross-functional interactions (5)
- I do not work directly with researchers or research teams (6)

Page Break

Q70 What types of challenges in your RCD Facilitation role require the most effort to manage or resolve?

End of Block: RCD Facilitation

Start of Block: End of Survey Text

T_Fin When you advance to the next screen you will be brought to the end of the survey and redirected to a Google Form for the Gift Card drawing. If you want to revise any responses do so now, otherwise continue and your responses will be submitted.

End of Block: End of Survey Text
